

ℓ -CATCH DIFFERENTIAL GAME FOR OBJECTS WITH DECREASING SPEEDS

Soyibboev Ulmasjon Boykuzi ugli

Namangan State University

e-mail: ulmasjonsoyibboev@gmail.com

Abdumannopov Muhammadsodik Muhammadyusuf ugli

Fergana State University

e-mail: muhammadsodiq1917@gmail.com

tel: +99899-975-98-38 (Soyibboyev O‘.B.)

tel: +99891-129-19-17 (Abdumannopov M.M.)

Annotation. *In the article, we have examined the ℓ -catch problem in a differential game with two players of a simple motion under exponentially decreasing geometric constraints on controls. The problem has been considered separating into two cases. To solve the ℓ -catch problem we have formulated an approach strategy for a pursuer and obtained sufficient conditions of ℓ -catch.*

Keywords. *Differential game, ℓ -catch, pursuer, evader, geometric constraint, strategy, guaranteed time of ℓ -catch.*

TEZLIKLARI KAMAYUVCHI OBYEKTLAR UCHUN ℓ -TUTISH DIFFERENSIAL O‘YINI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu maqola boshqaruvlarga eksponensial so‘nuvchi geometrik chegaralanishlar qo‘yilgan holda ikkita o‘yinchiga ega sodda harakatli differensial o‘yinda ℓ -tutish masalasi o‘rganilgan. Masalani yechishda ikkita holatga ajratilgan. ℓ -tutish masalasini yechish uchun quvlovchiga yaqinlashish strategiyasi qurilgan va ℓ -tutishning zaruriy va yetarli shartlari olingan.*

Kalit so‘zlar. *Differensial o‘yin, ℓ -tutish, quvlovchi, qochuvchi, geometrik chegaralanish, strategiya, kafolatlangan ℓ -tutish vaqti.*

ДИФФЕРЕНЦИАЛЬНАЯ ИГРА ℓ -ПОИМКА ДЛЯ ОБЪЕКТОВ С УБЫВАЮЩИХ СКОРОСТИ

Аннотация. *В этой статье мы исследуем задача ℓ -поймка в дифференциальной игре с двумя игроками простого движения при экспоненциально убывающих геометрических ограничениях на управления. Рассмотрена задача, разделенная на два случая. Для решения задачи ℓ -поймка сформулирована стратегия сближения преследователя и получены достаточные условия ℓ -поймка.*

Ключевые слова. *Дифференциальная игра, ℓ -поймка, преследователь, убегающий, геометрическое ограничение, стратегия, гарантированное время ℓ поймка.*

Suppose that in the finite-dimensional space $\mathbb{R}^n$, the pursuer (briefly, P) chases the evader (briefly, E). Let their motions be given by

$$P: \dot{x} = u, \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad (1)$$

$$E: \dot{y} = v, \quad y(0) = y_0, \quad (2)$$

where $x, y, u, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $n \geq 2$; x_0, y_0 are the initial states of the players P and E , which is supposed that $|x_0 - y_0| > \ell$, $\ell > 0$; the velocity vectors u, v in (1), (2) function as control parameters of the players P and E , respectively and they depend on the time $t \geq 0$.

The controls u, v are picked out as measurable functions $u(\cdot): \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $v(\cdot): \mathbb{R}_+ \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$, respectively and they are subject to the constraints

$$|u(t)| \leq \alpha e^{-pt} \text{ for almost every } t \geq 0, \quad (3)$$

$$|v(t)| \leq \beta e^{-qt} \text{ for almost every } t \geq 0, \quad (4)$$

which can be termed as exponentially decreasing geometric constraints (in short, G_e -constraints), where $p, q > 0$, $p \neq q$ and α, β are positive parametric numbers which express the maximal values of velocities of the players P and E , appropriately. The class of all measurable functions satisfying (3) is denoted by U_α^p , and the class of all measurable functions satisfying (4) is denoted by V_β^q .

For some $u(\cdot) \in U_\alpha^p$ and $v(\cdot) \in V_\beta^q$, from equations (1) and (2) the pairs $(x_0, u(\cdot))$ and $(y_0, v(\cdot))$ produce the trajectories of the players P and E , respectively:

$$x(t) = x_0 + \int_0^t u(s) ds, \quad y(t) = y_0 + \int_0^t v(s) ds.$$

The main objective of the pursuer is to converge the evader at the distance $\ell > 0$ (ℓ -catch problem), i.e., to achieve the relation

$$|x(\eta) - y(\eta)| \leq \ell \quad (5)$$

at some finite time $\eta > 0$. As to the evader strives to get out of the occurrence of (5) (evasion problem), i.e., to continue the inequality

$$|x(t) - y(t)| > \ell \quad (6)$$

for all $t \geq 0$, or if it is not possible, to prolong the instant η .

Let $z(t) = x(t) - y(t)$, $z(0) = z_0$. Then we have $z_0 = x_0 - y_0$.

Due to equations (1), (2), we obtain the unique Cauchy problem

$$\dot{z} = u - v, \quad z(0) = z_0. \quad (7)$$

Definition 1. In the game (1)–(4), we call the function

$$\mathbf{u}(t, v, z_0) = v - \lambda(t, v, z_0) \frac{\alpha z_0 e^{-pt} + v\ell}{\alpha e^{-pt} + \lambda(t, v, z_0)\ell} \quad (8)$$

an approach strategy of the pursuer in the time interval $[0, +\infty)$, where

$$\begin{cases} \lambda(t, v, z_0) = \frac{1}{h^2} \left[\langle v, z_0 \rangle + \alpha l e^{-pt} + \sqrt{\left(\langle v, z_0 \rangle + \alpha l e^{-pt} \right)^2 + h^2 \left(\alpha^2 e^{-2pt} - |v|^2 \right)} \right], \\ h^2 = |z_0|^2 - \ell^2. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2. In the game (1)–(4), we call the function

$$\mathbf{u}^*(t, v, z_0^*) = v - \lambda^*(t, v, z_0^*) \frac{\alpha z_0^* e^{-pt} + v\ell}{\alpha e^{-pt} + \lambda^*(t, v, z_0^*)\ell} \quad (9)$$

an approach strategy of the pursuer in the interval $[T_*, +\infty)$, $T_* = \frac{1}{p-q} \ln \frac{\alpha}{\beta}$, where

$$\begin{cases} \lambda^*(t, v, z_0^*) = \frac{1}{h_*^2} \left[\langle v, z_0^* \rangle + \alpha l e^{-pt} + \sqrt{\left(\langle v, z_0^* \rangle + \alpha l e^{-pt} \right)^2 + h_*^2 \left(\alpha^2 e^{-2pt} - |v|^2 \right)} \right], \\ h_*^2 = |z_0^*|^2 - \ell^2, \quad z_0^* = x_0 - y(T_*), \quad |z_0^*| = |z_0| + \frac{\beta}{q} \left(1 - \exp \left\{ \frac{q}{q-p} \ln \frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right\} \right). \end{cases}$$

Lemma 1. Let

$$\Lambda(t) = |z_0| - \frac{\alpha}{p} (1 - e^{-pt}) + \frac{\beta}{q} (1 - e^{-qt}) - \ell. \quad (10)$$

Then the equation $\Lambda(t) = 0$ has a unique positive root, which is represented by T_ℓ , in the following two cases:

a) on the interval $[0, T_*]$ if $\alpha > \beta$, $p > q$ and

$$|z_0| \leq \frac{\alpha}{p} - \frac{\beta}{q} + \ell + \alpha \left(\frac{p-q}{pq} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^{p/(q-p)};$$

b) in the interval $[0, +\infty)$ if $\alpha \geq \beta$, $p < q$ and $|z_0| < \frac{\alpha}{p} - \frac{\beta}{q} + \ell$.

Proof. c) By (10) we simply determine that $\Lambda(0) = |z_0| - \ell > 0$ and

$$\Lambda(T_*) = |z_0| - \frac{\alpha}{p} + \frac{\beta}{q} - \ell + \alpha \left(\frac{q-p}{pq} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^{p/(q-p)}. \text{ Further, } \Lambda'(t) < 0 \text{ for } t \in [0, T_*], \text{ that}$$

is, $\Lambda(t)$ is strongly decreasing on $[0, T_*]$. Since $\Lambda(T_*) \leq 0$ according to the conditions in (c), it follows that $\Lambda(t)$ vanishes at some $t \in [0, T_*]$.

d) As above, we have $\Lambda(0) = |z_0| - \ell > 0$ and $\Lambda'(t) < 0$ when $t \in [0, +\infty)$. Besides, from (10) and from the conditions in (d) we find

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \Lambda(t) = |z_0| - \frac{\alpha}{p} + \frac{\beta}{q} - \ell < 0.$$

Consequently, we can summarize that $\Lambda(t)$ reaches zero at some $t \in [0, +\infty)$. The proof has been completed.

Lemma 2. Let

$$\Lambda^*(t) = |z_0^*| - \ell + \alpha \left(\frac{p-q}{pq} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^{p/(q-p)} + \frac{\alpha}{p} e^{-pt} - \frac{\beta}{q} e^{-qt}. \quad (11)$$

Then the equation $\Lambda^*(t) = 0$ has a unique positive root, which is represented by T_ℓ^* , in the interval $[T_*, +\infty)$ if $\alpha < \beta$, $p < q$ and $|z_0^*| < \ell + \alpha \left(\frac{q-p}{pq} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^{p/(q-p)}$.

Proof. From (10) we get $\Lambda^*(T_*) = |z_0^*| - \ell > 0$ and $\frac{d\Lambda^*(t)}{dt} < 0$ in $[T_*, +\infty)$.

Moreover, from (11) and from the conditions in the lemma we obtain

$$\lim_{t \rightarrow +\infty} \Lambda^*(t) = |z_0^*| - \ell + \alpha \left(\frac{p-q}{pq} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^{p/(q-p)} < 0.$$

As a result, we can assert that $\Lambda^*(t)$ equals zero at some $t \in [T_*, +\infty)$. The proof has been finished.

Definition 3. In the game (1)–(4), the strategy (8) (the strategy (9)) is said to be *guaranteeing the occurrence of ℓ -approach on the interval*

$[0, T_\ell]$ (on the interval $[T_*, T_\ell^*]$) **if, for any control $v(\cdot) \in V_\beta^q$:**

1) a finite time $t_* \in [0, T_\ell]$ ($t_* \in [T_*, T_\ell^*]$), which $|z(t_*)| \leq \ell$ ($|z(t_*)| \leq \ell$) occurs, can be found;

2) the inclusion $\mathbf{u}(t, v, z_0) \in U_\alpha^p$ ($\mathbf{u}^*(t, v, z_0^*) \in U_\alpha^p$) is satisfied on the interval $[0, t_*]$ ($[T_*, t_*]$), where T_ℓ (T_ℓ^*) is the number stated in Lemma 3.7 (Lemma 3.8) and we call this *a guaranteed time of ℓ -catch*.

Theorem 1. If Lemma 1 (Lemma 2) is true, then the strategy (8) (the strategy (9)) will be guaranteeing the occurrence of ℓ -catch on the interval $[0, T_\ell]$ (on the interval $[T_*, T_\ell^*]$) in the game (1)–(4).

Proof. Let’s suppose that the pursuer utilizes the strategy (8), while the evader selects an arbitrary control $v(\cdot) \in V_\beta^q$. Then owing to (7), obtain the initial value problem

$$\dot{z} = \mathbf{u}(t, v(t), z_0) - v(t), \quad z(0) = z_0, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T_\ell. \quad (12)$$

$$\left(\dot{z} = \mathbf{u}^*(t, v(t), z_0^*) - v(t), \quad z(T_*) = z_0^*, \quad T_* \leq t \leq T_\ell^*. \quad (13) \right)$$

From (8) and (12) ((9) and (13)) we get the solution

$$z(t) = z_0 - \int_0^t \lambda(s, v(s), z_0) \frac{\alpha z_0 e^{-ps} + v(s)\ell}{\alpha e^{-ps} + \lambda(s, v(s), z_0)\ell} ds. \quad (14)$$

$$\left(z(t) = z_0^* - \int_{T_*}^t \lambda^*(s, v(s), z_0^*) \frac{\alpha z_0^* e^{-ps} + v(s)\ell}{\alpha e^{-ps} + \lambda^*(s, v(s), z_0^*)\ell} ds. \quad (15) \right)$$

Using the properties of module and taking (4) into consideration, we estimate the function (14) (the function (15)) from above as follows:

$$|z(t)| \leq |z_0| \left(1 - \alpha \int_0^t \frac{e^{-ps} \lambda(s, v(s), z_0)}{\alpha e^{-ps} + \lambda(s, v(s), z_0)\ell} ds \right) + \beta \ell \int_0^t (t-s) \frac{e^{-ps} \lambda(s, v(s), z_0)}{\alpha e^{-ps} + \lambda(s, v(s), z_0)\ell} ds$$

$$\left(|z(t)| \leq |z_0^*| \left(1 - \alpha \int_{T_*}^t \frac{e^{-ps} \lambda^*(s, v(s), z_0^*)}{\alpha e^{-ps} + \lambda^*(s, v(s), z_0^*)\ell} ds \right) + \beta \ell \int_{T_*}^t \frac{e^{-ps} \lambda^*(s, v(s), z_0^*)}{\alpha e^{-ps} + \lambda^*(s, v(s), z_0^*)\ell} ds \right)$$

or

$$|z(t)| \leq |z_0| - (\alpha |z_0| - \beta \ell) \int_0^t \frac{e^{-ps} \lambda(s, v(s), z_0)}{\alpha e^{-ps} + \lambda(s, v(s), z_0)\ell} ds. \quad (16)$$

$$\left(|z(t)| \leq |z_0^*| - (\alpha |z_0^*| - \beta \ell) \int_{T_*}^t \frac{e^{-ps} \lambda^*(s, v(s), z_0^*)}{\alpha e^{-ps} + \lambda^*(s, v(s), z_0^*)\ell} ds. \quad (17) \right)$$

Estimate the right-hand side of (16) (the right-hand side of (17)) and it follows the inequality

$$|z(t)| \leq |z_0| - \frac{\alpha}{p} (1 - e^{-pt}) + \frac{\beta}{q} (1 - e^{-qt}) = \Lambda(t) + \ell. \quad (18)$$

$$\left(|z(t)| \leq |z_0^*| + \alpha \left(\frac{p-q}{pq} \right) \left(\frac{\alpha}{\beta} \right)^{p/(q-p)} + \frac{\alpha}{p} e^{-pt} - \frac{\beta}{q} e^{-qt} = \Lambda^*(t) + \ell. \quad (19) \right)$$

On the basis of Lemma 1 (Lemma 2), there is a finite time $T_\ell \left(T_\ell^* \right)$ such that $\Lambda(T_\ell) = 0 \left(\Lambda^* \left(T_\ell^* \right) = 0 \right)$ is fulfilled. From this and from the inequality (18) (the inequality (19)) we take the desired result, i.e., $|z(T_\ell)| \leq \ell$ or $|x(T_\ell) - y(T_\ell)| \leq \ell$ $\left(|z(T_\ell^*)| \leq \ell$ or $|x(T_\ell^*) - y(T_\ell^*)| \leq \ell \right)$. **The proof is complete.**

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